

A Brief Study about Transgender

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Abstract

This paper provides a general sense of transgender studies in society. This review primarily focuses on knowledge that will benefit the transgender people and communities. It also focuses on cultural presentations, political movements, social organizations. The transgender studies also provide an interdisciplinary approach to gender studies. It includes transgender history, transgender literature, transgender psychology, and their health.

Keywords: Movements, Interdisciplinary, History.

A subfield of LGBT studies, transgender studies gives an interdisciplinary approach to gender studies, gay and lesbian studies, and sexology by studying the intersections of sex and gender as related to cultural representations, lived experience, and political movements. The transgender studies provide replies to negative aspects of beliefs about transgender people. Those negatives mistakes could be the narrow and inaccurate transgender state in psychology medicine and psychology. The final goal of transgender studies is to provide knowledge that will benefit the transgender people and communities.

In response to analyses of how transgender issues were represented in gender, gay and lesbian studies, the late 1990s saw an increase in transgender scholarship and the emergence of a specific discipline of academic research. Transgender history begins with transgender people in early cultures in every developed region and remains to the instant. Sumerian and Akkadian writings from 4500 years ago document transgender reverends, and Assyrian texts document trans prostitutes. The evidence suggests these gender roles to back to prehistoric times and may have a common origin with third gender roles were accepted in America before European colonization Some of which survived colonizers hostility.

Graves of transgender people in Europe and America have been identified from 4500 years ago, and likely depictions occur in art around the Mediterranean from 9000 to 3700 years ago. In those days in Greece, Phrygia and Rome, there were trans-female Galli priests and records of women dressing as men to vote, fight, study.

In the middle ages, accounts about Europe document trans men, while Kalonymu's lament for being born a man instead of a woman has been seen as an early account of gender diaspora. A male-bodied Briton captured in 1394 while living and acting sex work as a woman,

has been recognized as a trans woman. Transgender people are facing inequality and discrimination even before the 1880s. Some native American tribes had third-gender roles, including transgender people. When Europeans came over, they deemed them “berdaches” a derogatory term for a man trying to pass as a woman’s pejorative term for women who wanted to assume masculine roles. The name ‘transitive’ originated in 1910 from the German sexologist Magnus Hirschfeld. At that time, it was used similarly to transsexual, a word that was not coined until the late 1940s. The term transgender was first used in 1971.

Transgender people face inequality even when they try to begin their school education. A transgender person applied to school, and college was rejected because their home state identified as transgender. They gave first preference to ordinary human people and not transgender students. Mental and physical strain through varying forms of assault by their peers is an unfortunate effect on transgender students.

For instance, they have to face the embarrassing situation in the public restroom and whether they can use the male or female bathroom is choosing what restroom to use. While they enter into the lady’s toilet, women screamed in horror, and they will look like “you are not supposed to enter here/this is not a place for you” referring their gender though they did not confront them. They try to say that they are trans woman, and have every rights to use the toilet.

Media shows transgender as a sex worker and begging people in so many movies. The reality presented about transgender as sex workers are the view of entertainment. Transgender usually represented as roaming alone or group with brighter make-up, wigs glittering costumes and as calling the heroes and comedians for sexual relationships in media and showing innocents suffered by transgender, their social in certainty does not represent in any film and transgender people usually represented in songs, particularly songs which humiliate them in some movie.

While the transgender people traveling by bus or train they alienated by the other passengers. In case the transgender people sit along with them, they gave respect through Untouchability. Even if they are the standard genders like men and women are mistreating them with their misrepresentation names.

These things reflect the sick mentality of people. We have to respect them like other human beings. There is nothing to discriminate them. As a human being a part of society, we have the responsibility to produce them and respect them.

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